

FRACTURE PROCESSES IN MULTI-SCALED CARBON NANOTUBE/GLASS FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO FATIGUE LOADING

C. S. Grimmer¹, C. K. H. Dharan^{1*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of California, Berkeley, California 94720-1740, U.S.A.

*Corresponding author (dharan@me.berkeley.edu)

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1 Introduction

Damage mechanisms in conventional composite laminates subjected to cyclic loading are characterized by initiation and propagation of micro-cracks in the matrix that eventually result in fiber failure and laminate fracture [1,2]. In this work, we investigated the effect of adding smaller scale reinforcements, carbon nanotubes (CNTs), to determine if the resulting hierarchical composite will exhibit improved fatigue life.

The addition of CNTs is expected to generate multi-scale damage zones distributed in the form of a multitude of fine nano-scale cracks over large volumes that should be effective in retarding failure. In addition, fiber bridging at the nanoscale is likely to increase energy absorption through the participation of nanotubes in the fracture process further improving resistance to damage growth.

Fatigue loading scenarios investigated include uniaxial fatigue in the plane of the macro-scale fiber reinforcement, monotonic Mode I delamination and cyclic Mode I delamination.

2 Materials and Methods

The matrix epoxy resin and hardener used in this study was EPON 826 and Epikure 3234, respectively, both manufactured by Hexion Specialty Chemicals, Inc. (Houston, TX, USA). The EPON 826 resin was blended with 1% by weight of multi-walled CNTs by Nanoledge (Clapiers, France). The glass fiber reinforcement was Type 7500, a 0.28-mm thick plain weave fabric obtained from Hexcel (Fullerton, CA, USA).

Both the CNT and non-CNT [0/90] fiber-reinforced composites were manufactured by wet lay-up followed by post-curing. For all samples, fiber volume fraction was measured to be 0.56.

Both tapered and constant width delamination specimens were prepared with embedded PTFE tape at the mid-plane to create the initial pre-crack [3]. White correction fluid was painted along the edge of the samples so crack front advancement could be visually monitored. In order to maintain small deflections and linearity, the tapered-width delamination specimens were bonded on top and bottom to 3.4mm thick sheets of 6061-T6 aluminum, with a bond thickness of 0.13mm maintained by small sections of 36 AWG copper wire.

The in-plane and delamination specimens were monotonically and cyclically tested using an MTS (Eden Prairie, MN, USA) 100 kN servo-hydraulic testing machine retrofitted with a variable flow hydraulic supply digitally controlled by an Instron (Norwood, MA, USA) Labtronic 8400 controller. Real-time cyclic hysteresis and stiffness were monitored on a cycle-by-cycle basis using a custom LabVIEW v7 (National Instruments Austin, TX, USA) program. Representative fracture surfaces were excised from the test samples and sputter coated with a 2.5nm thick layer of platinum for imaging in a Hitachi S-5000 cold field emission high resolution SEM.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 In-plane Fatigue

Plots of cycles-to-failure versus peak alternating stress were produced with samples grouped by type, either with or without CNTs distributed in the matrix polymer. Each sample group consisted of four samples tested until gross failure was observed, all at a percentage of their pre-established monotonic failure strength. The S-N data obtained is plotted with lifetimes on a log scale (Fig. 1). Each point

represents the average and standard deviation of the four samples tested.

Fig. 1. Applied cyclic stress v. number of cycles to failure (in-plane cyclic loading)

3.2 Mode I Delamination

Measurements of G_{IC} , the critical strain energy release rate, were obtained from plots of the load-displacement profile for each of the delamination load-unload tests conducted on the constant width samples (Fig. 2). The energy for crack advancement is obtained from the area inside the curve for a single load-unload cycle that is normalized by the area of the new crack surface created, i.e.,

$$G_{IC} = \frac{\oint P d\delta}{w \Delta a} \quad (1)$$

Here, P is the applied load, δ is the grip displacement, w is the sample width and Δa is the incremental change in the crack length [4]. The measured mean and standard deviation of G_{IC} for the conventional and hybrid composites respectively were 790 (18.1) J/m² and 816 (23.3) J/m². The results were averaged over ten tests conducted on two samples for both the conventional and hybrid composites. Due to the relatively blunt nature of the PTFE pre-crack and the resulting inflation in the measured G_{IC} , the data from the initial pop-in cycle was discarded. Representative load-displacement loops are shown for a typical test in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Representative load-displacement loops used for determination of G_{IC} .

3.3 Cyclic Mode I Delamination

The tapered width delamination samples facilitated the stable measurement of crack propagation at sub-critical cyclic strain energy release rates. These measurements are then used to produce plots of crack advancement versus cyclic strain energy release rate. Analysis of these plots provides the constants, C and m from the power law equation, $da/dN = C \Delta a^m$ (Fig. 3).

Fig.3. Delamination cyclic crack growth per cycle v. applied cyclic strain energy release rate. C and m are fitted parameters in the equation: $da/dN = C(\Delta G)^m$.

A significant increase in the number of cycles-to-failure for each loading case was observed for the samples that contained the CNT-blended resin. The

observed increase in life occurs at lifetimes greater than 10^4 cycles. At these stress levels, the CNT-modified composite samples showed fatigue lives that were more than 2.5 times that of the unmodified composites in both in-plane fatigue and cyclic delamination loading.

The larger effect that the addition of CNTs has on fatigue life at low cyclic stress levels may be explained by first considering the observed failure mechanisms in glass fiber composites subjected to cyclic loading. Dharan showed that the fatigue life of glass fiber composites is related to the nucleation and growth of damage in the polymer matrix, and that damage in the matrix was found to be an accurate measure of the fatigue strength of the composite [1]. At high cyclic stress amplitudes, significant and extensive matrix damage is created in a few cycles. With continued cycling, damage in the form of relatively closely spaced cracks, propagates rapidly on several fronts until failure results. At low stress levels, damage in the matrix is limited; with continued cycling, a few cracks widely spaced propagate slowly until eventually, failure occurs.

Corroborating evidence of these mechanisms have been shown by other investigators for short and continuous glass fiber polymer composites [5-7].

The relative effectiveness of CNTs at low cyclic stress levels relative to high stress levels can be explained by strain energy considerations and the fatigue failure mechanisms described above. At high stress levels, the applied strain energy density is high and damage propagation occurs at several fronts and at a rapid rate. Under such conditions, obstacles, such as inclusions or, in this case, CNTs, are not very effective in slowing damage propagation, since the high stress intensities at the crack tips can overcome these obstacles in a few cycles. At low stress levels, however, damage propagation is slower and at a few widely spaced crack fronts whose progression can be slowed relatively effectively since a larger fraction of the strain energy must be dissipated in overcoming the obstacles [8-10]. Fig. 4 show a fatigue fracture surface indicating the scale difference and dispersion between the CNTs and glass fibers, and Fig. 5 shows CNTs pulled out or fractured in delamination cycling.

Fig.4. Fatigue fracture in CNT/glass fiber showing CNT pull-out and dispersion between the macro-scale reinforcement (higher magnification, right).

Fig. 5. SEM of cyclic delamination fracture surface showing fractured and pulled-out CNTs (arrow).

4 Energy Model

The intent of this section is to develop an energy based model that is able to shed light on the results presented here as well as predict the behavior of a general multi-scale laminate subjected to similar fatigue loading.

The observed inverse relationship between improvement in fatigue performance and the amplitude or intensity of the loading applied, implies that the underlying mechanism responsible for this improvement should be one that provides diminishing influence at higher applied loads.

Observation of the SEM imagery of the fracture surfaces associated with various applied loads reveals that the ratio of pulled-out CNTs to fractured CNTs is inversely proportional to this applied load.

These two observations give rise to a general energy based matrix damage model:

$$E_T = E_{MF} + [E_{PO} \times f] + [E_{CF} \times (1 - f)] \quad (2)$$

where E_T is the total energy absorbed by the matrix prior to composite failure, E_{MF} is the energy associated with creating the critical density of matrix cracks for failure, E_{CP} and E_{CF} are the energies related to CNT pull-out and fracture, respectively, and f is the fraction of CNTs that pull-out rather than fracture. With this fraction assumed to be described as

$$f \propto \text{applied load}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Table 1 shows the fraction of pulled-out CNTs as a function of applied cyclic strain energy release rate as observed in representative fracture surface images.

ΔG [J/m ²]	f
223	0.56
430	0.39
830	0.26

Table 1. CNT pull-out fraction as a function of applied cyclic strain energy release rate

Setting the energy of CNT pullout to be equal to the energy dissipated through friction at the interface between the CNTs and the surrounding matrix polymer gives

$$E_{PO} = \left(\frac{\tau_p S_p \delta_p}{2} \right) \times N_{CNT} \quad (4)$$

where τ_p , S_p and δ_p are the frictional shear stress at the interface, the area of the interface and the distance over which sliding takes place, respectively, and N_{CNT} is the number of CNTs that are involved in the fracture process per unit area of crack surface created. Additionally the energy of CNT fracture can be described as

$$E_{CF} = (n_c \xi_c) \times N_{CNT} \quad (5)$$

where n_c and ξ_c are the number of carbon-carbon bonds broken in the fracture of an individual CNT and the carbon-carbon bond strength, respectively. Simplifying (2) and assuming that E_{MF} is unchanged from the traditional composite to the multi-scale composite, gives the following differential energy equation

$$\Delta E = \left[\left(\frac{\tau_p S_p \delta_p f}{2} \right) + (n_c \xi_c)(1-f) \right] N_{CNT} \quad (6)$$

This equation represents the energy dissipated in the matrix of the multi-scale composite in J/m² due to both pullout and fracture of the CNTs. It is this increase in matrix energy dissipation in a way that does not promote crack advancement that is believed to be the underlying cause for the observed improvements in fatigue lifetimes in multi-scaled composites.

Solving for the various constants in the differential energy equation for a given CNT-based multi-scale composite and applying them to the cyclic strain energy release rate observed in a traditional composite has shown promise as a means of predicting the fatigue behavior of the multi-scale composites [10].

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